

Recent Youth Protests and Democracy in India Specific Reference to Student Youth

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Abstract

Youth are the future of every society. Societies, where good quality resources are provided to Youth, have higher results for their future than compared to a society where Youth are neglected. India is the youngest country, and her youth population is the highest globally. Recently, events in Indian politics have seen the participation of Indian Youth, especially university students, but the nature of these protests concerns the Indian state. These protests targeted Indian state and supported anti-national elements like separatist movements, anti-India elements and so on. They are blaming everything upon government without adequately dealing with issues.

Key words: Youth, Protests, Students, State.

Introduction

In recent years, we have witnessed youth agitation against their government; these agitations are coming out as anti-government protests worldwide. In the Indian neighborhood, we had recent student movements where the government had to fall due to student protests. Youth of any country are essential for its society. Youth are the upcoming citizens of country. Youth is the age full of energy and capacity to do anything. Currently, the youth population of India is the highest in the world, which allows India to climb to the new highest in world leadership. Indian Youth are optimistic about politics and its possibilities of changes, they want politics, where development, work free of corruption, leadership with vision and so on is primary requirement. Youth politics in recent times has two paths: participation in democratic and electoral politics, where youth-supported leadership prioritizes development issues, good leadership, and so on. In the second way, Youth came to streets showing their anger against ill practises. In this, some particular elements of politics tried to take advantage of Youth politics, for example, the JNU anti-India slogan.

Research Objective

The research objective is to talk about the Youth political movement in India and the recent radicalization of students on Indian university campuses and the reasons for it.

Literature review

H. C. Upreti, (1987) Youth politics in India, Printwell Publishers, Jaipur (India)

The book describes Youth Politics in India and reasons for youth politics in colleges and university campuses of India.

Sanjay Kumar and Praveen Rai (2014) Indian Youth and Electoral Politics: An Emerging Engagement by, Sage publications.

Book is describing electoral preferences of Youth of India. They talk about behaviour of Youth are also shaped by their education, location, caste, class and so on

Edited Sanjay Kumar (2019) Youth in India Aspirations, Attitudes, Anxieties, published by Routledge.

Book talk about Indian Youth their background and their choices. Despite globalization, the Youth of India have different takes on marriage, education, jobs, and so on.

OECD, Youth stocktaking Report, 2017

This report is essential in understanding the current situation of the Youth; they have challenges like inequality and climate change, plus the Youth of OECD countries are showing less trust in their government.

LSE Enterprise, January 2013, Youth participation in Democratic life.

Report talk about Youth and their participation in democratic life. The report describes the current situation and how (new)media is bringing a new dimension to participation.

Problem definition

The research paper wants to point out student youth radicalization in universities and its target on the ruling government.

Research Method

Research paper is written after using books, reports, and articles from sources like online websites and newspapers.

Youth Politics Around the World in Recent Times

Present time democratic system and its relationship youth in sorry conditions. Youth are losing interest in Democracy. Major reasons are corruption, ineffective leadership, instability and so on. Declining youth interest in Democracy is becoming a major trend in the world. Democracy of the West, Arab world, and Africa is witnessing decreasing interests of youths, but in India, this is not the case. Youth often support new trends and movements, bringing new life to our society, culture and so on. In Western democracy, Youth are getting more apolitical and showing interest in other things than participation; this is also the same in Africa and Arab and so on. In Africa, Youth are less interested in Democracy. After continue corruption and fail of leadership. In Arab, its same ineffective leadership and corruption make youths less interested in Democracy.

Report "Youth Participation in Democratic Life" in 2013 by LSE enterprise said youth participation in Democracy across Europe and other part is declining. They are dissatisfied by the way Democracy is governing. "Global Satisfaction with Democracy 2020" report by future of Democracy said peoples are unhappy with Democracy and dissatisfaction is growing. Again "Youth and Satisfaction with Democracy in 2020 report" by Centre for the future of Democracy said youth satisfaction with Democracy is declining.

"Freedom in the World" 2022 report by Freedom House again repeated the sad status of similar issues with Democracy.

Summary report "the role of Youth in Democratic Resilience", Oct 2018 by community of Democracies said Democracy's resilience is weakening, xenophobia and social polarization is increasing and Youth faith is also decreasing in Democracy.

So, we can conclude from these reports that Youth are not showing enough interest and participation in Democracy and this trend is growing over the years. In recent times, Youth, particularly in Western countries and the world, are not showing interest in Democracy and elections, which is a dangerous trend.

In **African Countries**, Youth are not support of democratic system. They believe that it's inevitable to be corrupt in Democracy. Young people are not very keen of Democracy.

In **Arab world**, Democracy is also seeing lesser support; it's in danger of decline. Youth even believe that it's inevitable to be corrupt in Democracy. These youths have no problem with other forms of government in place of Democracy. These forms are mainly monarchy-based system.

Western Countries' Youth are not participating in more significant numbers, which is causing danger and support for no democratic trends.

Robert Putnam talks about decline of social capital. Social norms and collective values are in decline and individualism is increasing. At present, time Youth in the West and certain parts of the world, like the Arabic world, are losing their interest in Democracy; they believe it's inevitable to corrupt

Democracy, and they are not against other forms of government. But this process is not everywhere in the world developing countries like India and so on, in these countries youth are interested in Democracy and want to bring improvements in this system.

In recent times, the Youth movement are connecting to social media. Social media is playing vital role in this. Social media is bringing news or events worldwide to our cell phones directly. Work like "Youthquake2017, The Rise of the Young Cosmopolitans in Britain" by **James Sloam and Matt Henn** said now Youth are opting for non-electoral forms of politics through boycotts and petitions. In this social media is playing vital role.

Youth protest Indian neighbourhood: Sri Lanka and Bangladesh.

In Sri Lanka, a few years back, we saw youth power. In the country, the government could not handle the economic situation, which created chaos and resulted in Youth of the country launching movement against government. And ultimate result was fall of the government.

The same type of youth movement happened in Bangladesh, the reason for student and youth anger was that the government again allowed reservations for freedom fighters of Bangladesh freedom from country. this act resulted in Youth coming to the streets, and a huge movement was built up against the ruling government. This movement resulted in the fall of the government in the country; Bangladesh PM Sheikh Hasina had to leave the country and reach India. Country went to chaos and interim government is found in country; head of government is Muhammad Yunus became PM of country but there is not stop in attack against minorities especially Hindus.

Youth in India and Political Participation

But trends in India are reverse of these; presently India is youngest country in the world. In the country's total population, many of the population is Youth and under 25. It has lots of potential to deliver to country and world. Youth of India are more interested in politics and participation. Youths of India also show their anger whenever it is needed, but the primary method for this is non-violence. They are interested in entry of Youths leadership in politics, they want Youth to more and more participate in politics. In youths, girls or ladies are also interested in politics; they want to participate in politics because their numbers are lower than boys in terms of politics and participation.

Youth politics in India always remains essential before and after freedom, earlier time of colonization youth participated in politics through non-violent and violent ways primary example is Bhagat Singh and his friends. They killed the English police officers for brutality toward Indians, mainly being responsible for the death of Lala Lajpat Rai. Another example is Sardar Udham Singh, he killed police officer involved in murder of people in Jallianwala Bagh. He went to Britain to take revenge of it.

Youth also participated in non- violent movements of Gandhi and so on. youth joined in numbers to Gandhi and his movements. They boycott English good and product and so on. they supported Gandhi to hold strong protest against British rule.

After freedom of the country, Youth did not hesitate from participating politics. These movements were both non-violent and violent movements. Earlier movements for Youth to create a state based on linguistic identities in the 1950s were focused on Odisha, Madras, and so on.

It was Naxalism movements, which also attracted Youth in 1960s. This movement was famous in rural areas but urban areas also, and lots of urban Youth join this. Movement one time was the biggest internal security threat for the country but recently there has been a decline in movement growth.

But after independence famous example of youth movement is **J.P Andolan**. Jai Prakash Narayan lead this movement, he is also known as Jan Nayak. It was the participation of the Youth that was responsible for challenging the Indira Gandhi government. Through this movement, a lot of leaders came to Indian politics. Famous were Lalu Prasad Yadav, Nitish Kumar, Ram Vilas Paswan, and so on. this movement was again completely non-violent movement. In result, Indira Gandhi was forced to declared emergence.

Students also participated in movements of **AASU** in Assam, which resulted in emergence of **the Assam Gana Parishad Party**. This party successfully win power in Assam's politics but failed to deliver its promises. This is one of India's most prominent examples of student or youth protests.

After this, Youth participated in **Nirbhaya and Anna movements**. These movements created a lot of pressure over government and these movements were considered responsible for the decline of Congress government.

In Nirbhaya movement, people came openly to show their anger over brutal rape in Delhi. incident became so important that it became a headache for the Delhi government run by Sheila Dixit. Ultimately this movement was responsible for decline of Sheila Dixit's Congress government in Delhi.

Anna movement gave birth to AAP party and leader Arvind Kejriwal. During Anna's movement, corruption became a major issue. People blame the ruling Congress government for this.

Youth also supported Narendra Modi in 2014 and 2019 Lok Sabha elections. It was Youth supported, which help Modi in gaining massive landslide victory. Modi was very famous among Youth, they vote for him in large numbers. In vote shares of BJP, Youth votes share played significant role.

Recently, we have witnessed student protests against the government and its policies. But sometimes, these protests also raise issues or slogans, which discomfort the whole nation and raise issues about Indian sovereignty. These students protest broke out in Delhi, Hyderabad, Aligarh and Jadavpur based central university. In universities of Delhi, JNU and Jamia Millia Islamia were major centres.

In JNU, a group of unknown students chanted anti-India slogans, which brought a lot of buzz in the media and the country. Result of this several students were investigated and some arrested by police, major names in these protests were Kanhaiya Kumar and Umar Khalid and so on.

Police later arrested Kanhaiya Kumar and Umar Khalid for promoting protest in JNU. For many days, this incident became a hot topic on TV and social media. In present time, Kanhaiya Kumar is Congress politician and Umar Khalid is in jail and facing trail.

In Jamia Milia University, police had to crack down and lathi charge when students were holding dharna; recently, some student groups tried to create a political environment, but they failed this time. University students protested against the CAA (Citizenship Amendment Act) and NRC (National Register of Citizens) in 2019.

In Hyderabad, students held protests after the death of fellow student Rohit Vemula, resulting in a lot of media coverage and media attention. This act tried to ruined image university and VC. Though after report by district scrutiny committee in Andhra Pradesh said neither Rohit or nor his mother is Dalit.

At Aligarh Muslim University, politics started happening when the Citizenship Amendment Act discussion started, and students held a dharna against the government and accused minority repression.

Case of Youth Political Participation in Uttarakhand

Uttarakhand was established on 9 November 2000 along with Chhattisgarh and Jharkhand. State was separated from Uttar Pradesh. It was neglected in Uttar Pradesh, plus the state's culture was different from Uttar Pradesh.

Talking about state politics, the BJP and Congress two parties dominate the state. The party of the Uttarakhand movement, Uttarakhand Kranti Dal, has hardly any presence in the state and is near to end. The state's politics always revolve around development, migration, and so on.

Regarding the state's challenges, migration is the biggest challenge; Youth have to migrate for employment, health, education, and so on. Earlier, the state used to be a hub for jobs in the Army, but after the launch of the Agni veer scheme, the question of employment will be worst and worst. After this comes Development, and other issues, development is serious need of the state. State have lack of basic facilities like education, health, roads, and so on.

Working age population state currently rises by 14% but employment decrease is not increasing, it declined from 30.43% in December 2021 to 40.10% in December 2016. Youth of all age group were mostly in the support of BJP (1) Age group 18 to 25, it was 25% (2) 25 to 33 age group, it was 67% 2019 Lok Sabha election in Uttarakhand. Youth from backward and lower castes supported BJP. For them, issues of Development, Good leadership, and so on were important.

In Uttarakhand Youth supported issues of leadership, development, corruption free work, issue of employments and so on. Youth and their issues are dominating in politics; every political party and political leader is claiming to have the support of youths.

But Youth of state also protest for their demand especially job frauds or paper leaks. This protest happened in the Dehradun, where large numbers of Youth gathered and protested, but the police answered with a lathi charge, which resulted in chaos and injuries to the Youth.

These youth and student movements are attempting to create a particular image of the government, where the student movement focused on repression and authoritarian nature. Still, things didn't succeed for the creator of these movements. We can say that youth politics in India recent time took two shapes. One through Democratic politics and Second using protest, dharanas and so on but believe in Democracy and non-violent ways remains well accepted. Youth of India are not remained silent whenever time to express their voice or angers to our representative governments, those are responsible for making good policy, society and so on for we the peoples of India. Experience of India is also important for Youth of world especially for those countries, where Youth are losing interest in Democracy and politics. Indian experience is mainly about youths believe in Democracy and method of non-violent, which is still primary method is showing anger and bringing change. Non-violent method can be crucial in Youth and their way of showing their anger in Democracy worldwide. Youth of world should not demoralize with leadership and corruption in their countries and should encourage youth participation and non-violent method of struggle.

Discussion

Overall analysis of these protest and youth politics in India, we can say Youths of India are still residing their faiths in Democracy. They supported Narendra Modi and his government democratically, but Youth earlier supported other leaders like Rahul Gandhi and Akhilesh Yadav in UP. Youth support to movements like Anna and so on was a clear example of peace and faith in Democracy, but recent incidents in JNU and other universities were the reverse of this. In the politics of India, there are few elements in our society which are encouraging certain sections of Youth in their ways of politics, which is helping their interests' fulfilments.

Conclusion

Youth politics of India is the crucial mode. Our youths still believe in Democracy and that it should deliver good for them, but they also open their ways to democratically raise their voice, where the ruling government has to pay attention to their demands. Youth should understand that current student led protests are not focusing the issue of actual needs like employment, health and so on. they are misguided and seeking to divert precious energy of Youth for their political motive. There is following ways to deal with these types of incident-

1. Not allowing unnecessary political process in campus by political motivated student groups.
2. There should be a watch on-campus activities and identify unnecessary political activism.

Future scope

This paper is essential in understanding India's youth politics and neighborhoods like Bangladesh in the upcoming years. Because Youth are very very active in politics of this country and their support is always essential for any political party.

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